

Assessment of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning Activities among State Tertiary Institutions Lecturers in Yobe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined assessment of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State, Nigeria. In line with the stated objective, one corresponding research question was raised and one null hypothesis was formulated for the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study consists of 2447 (2050 male and 397 female) lecturers during the 2021/2022 academic session in all the state tertiary institutions of learning in Yobe State. 333 (249 male and 84 female) lecturers constitute the sample size of the study using stratified sampling technique. Self-developed questionnaire titled “Assessment of Information and Communication Technology on Teaching and Learning Questionnaire” (AICTTLA) was used. Pilot test was conducted and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data collected in the study were presented in a tabular form and responses were calculated using frequency counts and percentages. The formulated hypothesis was tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that: Inadequate Information and Communication Technology gadgets, Provision of an e-learning system to store research materials negatively impacted academic staff performance in tertiary institutions in Yobe State. Therefore, the following recommendations were made; adequate capacity-building training for staff on the need to make the best use of ICT to justify the significant investment made by the tertiary institutions among others.

Keywords: Information, Communication, Technology, Teaching, Learning

Introduction

Technological advancement in the 21st Century has necessitated its adoption by institutions of higher learning globally such as colleges of education, polytechnics and universities for carrying out its core function of teaching, learning and the promotion of research activities of staff, students and other external partners. The adoption of information and communication technologies by tertiary institutions has positioned staff and students to have the privilege of accessing different information materials and also to learn at their own convenient time and place. In support of this assertion, Petrides and Nodine (2003) cited in Lawrence, (2019) opined that the growth and development of tertiary institutions lie squarely on the knowledge they created, the medium of transferring the knowledge they created to others and the relationship they are able to establish with other sister institutions.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT), has become an integral part of every aspect of human endeavour. The use of ICT extends from health care, education and governance, to entertainment. ICT has brought about significant changes in the way people communicate, share information and conduct various activities (Fakandu, 2019). In tertiary institutions, the use of ICT has enhanced the teaching and learning and impacted the overall growth of their institutions. ICT has been a key factor in improving teaching and learning activities in tertiary institutions. The use of computers, software applications and internet facilities has enabled academic staff members to carry out their duties efficiently and effectively. With the use of ICT, lecturers can easily keep track of students' progress, communicate with other staff and carry out administrative duties such as grading and attendance keeping. Similarly, Adeoye, Oluwole, and Loto, (2013) cited in Oyedokun, and Adeolu-Akande, (2022) maintained that ICT can make the tertiary institutions more efficient and productive, through its variety of tools to enhance and facilitate teachers' professional activities. ICT is the application of technology to communicate, share, retrieve and transmit

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information through electronic means. With the increase in the use of technology in various fields, educational institutions are no exception. The use of ICT in teaching, learning and research has become an essential aspect of tertiary institutions.

Teaching and learning are two processes that work together to change students' knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and behaviors. The teacher and learners engage with content in a classroom setting that is supportive of learning, using appropriate approaches and mediums. At every level particularly at the tertiary level of education, the main purpose of instruction is to substantially change the student. According to Ayeni (2011) cited in Isa et al (2020), teaching can be defined as a systematic process of transmitting knowledge, attitudes and skills in accordance with professional principles. In the traditional epoch, many teaching practitioners widely apply teacher-centered methods to impart knowledge to learners compared to student-centered methods. The ideal situation in Yobe State tertiary institutions would involve the effective integration and utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning activities. This would enhance student engagement, improve academic achievement and foster innovation and academic excellence.

However, the real situation in the state tertiary institutions presents a significant gap in the effective application and utilization of ICT in teaching and learning activities. According to the the present state of ICT utilization in education at all levels is not commensurate to the public attention generated over the years (Onwuagboke, et al. 2015) need for ICT integration for effective instructional delivery in Nigerian tertiary institutions (Yobe State tertiary institution inclusive) as various in Nigerian schools is at low ebb (Awolaye, et al 2008, Jude, et al. 2012). The persistence of this problem can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, there is inadequate ICT infrastructure and resources, such as computer laboratories, effective internet connectivity and up-to-date software and hardware in some of the tertiary institutions. This hampers the application and effective utilization of ICT in teaching and learning activities. Additionally, there are inadequate training and professional development opportunities for academic staff to acquire the necessary digital skills and knowledge required for successful ICT application.

The implications of not addressing this problem are significant. Without the effective integration and application of ICT in teaching and learning activities, state tertiary institutions may struggle to meet global educational standards and keep up with the evolving demands of the 21st-century workforce. This could result in a lack of competitiveness and hinder the overall development and progress of the educational sector in the state. To address this issue, this study intends to propose a unique intervention focused on enhancing ICT infrastructure, providing comprehensive training programmes for academic staff and developing policies that promote the effective application of ICT in teaching and learning activities. Therefore, it is against this backdrop, that, the study assessed the integration of ICT on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in state tertiary institutions in Yobe State, Nigeria.

The Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to:

Assess the mean response of application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among state tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study consists of 2447 (2050 male and 397 female) lecturers during the 2021/2022 academic session in all the state tertiary institutions of learning in Yobe State. 333 (249 male and 84 female) lecturers constitute the sample size of the study using a stratified sampling technique. A self-developed questionnaire titled "Assessment of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching and Learning Questionnaire" (AICTTLA) was used. The Instrument was divided into two sections (A & B). Section "A" deals with the types of institutions of the respondents, while section B deals with data related to the research questions raised. The questions posed for the study guided the construction of the questionnaire which was structured as strongly agree (SA) = 5 Points, Agree (A) = 4 Points, Undecided (UD) = 3 Points, disagree (D) = 2 Points and strongly disagree (SD) = 1 point. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by experts in the Department of Education, Yobe State University, Damaturu. To determine the reliability of the instrument, copies of the instrument were administered to a sample of 25 respondents in College of Education and Legal Studies, Nguru who were not part of the study. Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to analyze the

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data. The computation gave a reliability index of 0.87. The instrument was administered personally to the respondents by the researcher and three other research assistants. A total of 333 copies of the instruments were administered and retrieved. Data collected were analyzed using frequency, mean and standard deviation, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

The non-parametric statistical tool of F-test One-way ANOVA was used for data analysis which allows us to make a conclusion and the summary as presented in Table 2.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the application of Information and Communication Technology on teaching and learning activities among lecturers in state tertiary institutions lecturers in Yobe State.

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of ICT on Teaching and Learning Activities among Lecturers in State Tertiary Institutions in Yobe State

Status	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-crit.	P.Value	Decision
Between Groups	14.492	3	4.831	1.065	5.05	0.32	Retained
Within Groups	231.175	300	.955				
Total	245.557	333					

Source: Field Survey, (2023)

Table 2 shows the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test. It revealed that the calculated f-ratio value of 1.065 is less than the 5.05 F-critical value while the calculated P-value of 0.32 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance set for the study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on the impact of knowledge of ICT on academic staff performance in tertiary institutions in Yobe State.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 1 was an analysis of the respondents' opinions on information and communication technology teaching and learning activities among lecturers in state tertiary institutions. From the details provided in the table, it is clear that the majority of the respondents' integration of ICT enhances the efforts of the lecturers to enhance teaching and learning which leads to innovation in my institution. Also, the use of ICT in the teaching and learning process has been shown to improve academic staff productivity. This was in keeping with Onodugo, et al.'s (2015) assertion that ICT can become a major tool for enhancing academic staff performance in tertiary institutions by boosting the quality of teaching, learning, and research. Other research projects have been conducted to evaluate the effects of ICT in the field of education. Solar et al (2013) cited in Wael, (2018) stated that implementing ICT promotes learning and raises educational standards. This is in line with the findings of a study by Gallego et al. (2014), who contend that effective ICT policies and regulations must be implemented nationwide for a country to successfully increase the quality of education.

Conclusion

The study examined how ICT enhance teaching and learning in tertiary institutions and calls for a multifaceted approach that takes into account infrastructure, the requirement for ongoing training and development programs to improve academic staff members' ICT skills, and the integration of ICT into curricula to improve teaching and learning activities.

Recommendations

Following are some recommendations based on the findings:

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The management of tertiary institutions should propose a unique intervention focused on enhancing ICT infrastructure, providing comprehensive training programmes for academic staff and developing policies that promote the effective application of ICT in teaching and learning activities.

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